

A Process Framework For Nurturing Innovative Culture in Organisation in Commercial Motor Vehicle Sector

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Abstract : The study has focussed on the aspect of sustainable competitive advantage and proposed a CCC framework. The proposed framework is a holistic approach to engage the three stakeholders namely Customer- Company- Channel and propose an operating mechanism within each vertical to build efficiency through value addition/ value engineering by looking inwards yet increasing the organisational capability by increasing the horizons in value generation and adopting new technology. The CCC framework introduces the concept of Domain Expert Group [DEG] of Customers that helps Channel and Company co-create a value or product or any non-product offering to improve customer's profitability. On the company's front, the framework introduces the concept of 'Mission Summit' team that filters the ideas generated within or outside the organisation with Core team members CTMs through business case, proto building, testing to launch. It also aids in determining the connection between innovation and intrapreneurship and helps understand the extent to which intrapreneurial culture reinforces long-term, sustainable organisational growth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Jugaad, Innovation, Commercial motor vehicle and Transformation

JEL Classification:M120, O350, O310

1. Introduction

Owing to rapid technological advancement, Chen S et al.(2023), and the effects of globalisation, the need for attentiveness of all workforces with unique abilities and abilities that can make them think laterally or outside the box to extend solutions to the current and

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upcoming challenges is confronted by the firms through intrapreneurial initiatives, Bimpitsos (2012), Obeidat et al. (2014). An unprecedented genetic shift is taking place in the world of the automobile. The transition of internal combustion engines to battery, Wappelhorst (2023) and hydrogen fuel, Aminudin et al. (2023) is causing significant disruptions in transportation, along with 'Pay by mile', SA Soccolich, et al. (2013), Poole Jr R. W (2023), autonomous driving (Teng, S,2023), digitalization through connected vehicles, Bravo Rodríguez, (2023), and many other factors. Every stakeholder in the chain is being impacted by this shift in every possible way, Desreveaux, A et al. (2023).

Technological changes and modern innovations impact and promote the intrapreneurial culture in companies which could lead to sustainable competitive advantages, Laužikas, M et al.(2022). Therefore, encouraging Corporate Entrepreneurship or Intrapreneurship in organization's strategy is becoming a key and crucial way to connect with rigid bureaucratic institutions, Dess et al. (2003). In order to encourage intrapreneurship among the staff and to make this industry transition seamless and effective, the innovative culture, which unites individuals in the ways they think, work, and interact, will be a significant factor. To raise the value of stakeholders both inside and outside the organisation, leaders concentrate on innovative culture in order to favourably influence the ecosystem of talent management, maximise return on investment, and factors that stimulate innovation. In the manufacturing industry, the innovation quotient determines how to optimise overhead costs, make customer acquisition costs competitive, and lower total cost of ownership. With the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, organisational culture has become one of the most popular and extensively investigated issues. For developing and maintaining organisational success, it is now essential to use creative methods and approaches. Organizational culture and inventive culture are the establishments' saviours in this regard, Aksa (2011). Innovation and innovative culture are important for social and economic progress. Moreover, innovation is the main driver of social economic progress and competitiveness, Dundar, (2014). It is recorded by Legatum institute that 81% of the Indian businessmen said that '*Jugaad*' is the key reason for their success. Jugaad is the flexible approach to solve a problem with limited resources in hand which is called 'Innovation by constraint' or 'Frugal engineering'.

On other hand, there are substantial articles on how national culture affects the style of operation of business especially R&D, manufacturing and production centres. The differences in understanding the value system have an impact on the innovation in each of the operating function of the company. This collective programming of mind, which distinguishes one group of people behaviour from another.

It turns out that having a healthy and sustainable national economy, organisations depends on innovative corporate cultures and intrapreneurship activities. So, the development of intrapreneurship to achieve an organization's aims and goals appears to be a fundamental

necessity. The establishment expects its employees to carry out their duties with an inventive approach. Using all production elements for organisational and individual goals is of infinite significance to advance the level of social welfare advancement because people are constantly searching for new ideas and opportunities in a dangerous and unstable environment, Demirel and Tikici (2004). A result of creative culture is the absorption and adoption of intrapreneurship. Establishments are eager to promote any innovative culture that has the ability to respond swiftly, achieve the aims and objectives, and transform quicker than their rivals in a rapidly shifting, aggressive, and competitive environment. In order to communicate ideas about the effects of intrapreneurship on corporate culture, the study concentrates on the aspects of employee creativity.

2. Review of Literature

2.1 Manufacturing Organizations -Commercial Motor Vehicle

Any vehicle used to move goods or persons for the benefit of a person or business is referred to as a commercial motor vehicle (CMV). Examples of CMVs include taxis, trailers, and travel trailers in addition to box trucks, pickup trucks, vans, semi-trucks, buses, and coaches. Organization Internationale des Constructeurs d'Automobiles (OICA) reports that 26,286,317 commercial vehicles will be sold in 2021, up from 27,191,615 commercial vehicles in 2019 and 24,857,167 commercial vehicles in 2020. The commercial vehicle industry is expected to be worth USD 821.28 billion in 2021. The market is expected to grow at 8.7% CAGR from 2022 to 2029, reaching USD 1,712.44 billion from USD 955.57 billion. The unprecedented and disastrous COVID-19 epidemic has caused demand for commercial vehicles to be lower than anticipated in all regions when compared to pre-pandemic levels. OICA estimates that between 2019 and 2020, the worldwide market lost 10.2% of its value. Programs to develop and employ freight vehicles for transportation are being started in numerous countries. Continuous technical development is taking place in the field of freight vehicles, and some of these developments are quickly becoming requirements. The manufacturing of commercial vehicles is an international business, and automotive Original Equipment Manufacturers face several difficult obstacles. The degree of localisation and customization that commercial vehicle manufacturers can provide their products in diverse regions is currently up for debate. The major issue is creating platform strategies, modularization plans, market entry strategies, and adaptive business models that reduce uncertainty and place truck manufacturers and bus companies in a successful position. Few organisations assist manufacturers of commercial vehicles in reaching global markets, modifying products for local demands, and building up adaptable global manufacturing networks.

2.2 Innovation in Commercial Sector

The Merriam-Webster online dictionary states that innovation is the "act or process of implementing novel concepts, innovations, or methods. "Innovare" is a Latin term with the meaning "Innovation is derived from the verb "innovate," which means to create something new. Simply described, innovation is the successful implementation of novel concepts. Ultimately, it is evident that innovation is now essential to the survival of a company. Companies nowadays operate in a market that is always evolving as well as a complex and competitive environment. In order to maintain a dominant position on the global market, organisations must raise the number of their innovations and develop new products, services, or business strategies. In addition, client needs (such as luxury, safety, fuel efficiency, etc.), international competition, and environmental regulations and norms might spur manufacturers to develop new products in the automotive industry. The study on the status of innovation in automotive enterprises, Vikas (2018) reveals a variety of innovation types, including those involving goods, business or strategy concepts, services, processes, value, finance, marketing, etc. According to Rothberg's (1981) theory, a company's product innovation involves alterations or additions to the items that make up its product range. Innovative products can give businesses a competitive edge by capturing a share of the present market or opening up new, untapped markets by standing out from the competition. Process innovation may be defined as a successful process modification or enhancement that gives the organisation a significant competitive edge over its competitors. Building a competitive advantage may involve organisational changes that result in distinction in value, time-to-market, after-market support, etc. Schilling (2005) stated that increasing production proficiency or competence is typically associated with process improvements. As a result, changes in the process may not always be apparent to the client. For instance, actions that affect an organization's competitive advantage internally, such as knowledge management, organisational learning, and change management, can go unnoticed by customers. As can be seen, just like with products, a technique need not be entirely original to qualify as an innovation. The term "strategic innovation" refers to creativity that is linked to a company's strategy, which is the third type of innovation. Furthermore, it must be emphasised that strategy innovation does not necessarily entail a complete change in strategy and can be limited to minor adjustments or additions to an existing business concept, so long as it can be effectively tested and ensures a solid market position. Hence, a competitive advantage may come from strategy innovation through administration and positioning that provides long-term differentiation and encourages product and process innovation. To assist a business proactively position itself against competitors, strategic differentiation can establish new markets, foresee future markets, or revitalise existing markets, Baker (2002),

Hamel (1996). Disruptive innovation is defined as "the alteration of business models and value networks by technology or commercial innovation" EY (2016). Disruptive innovation is characterised by the entry of new services or products at the bottom of a mature market, the launch of such innovations by non-consumers at a lower price point than the industry leaders who are already established. Previous owners of these products or services who were unable to purchase them due to the price or lack of availability, Imber (2013). The organisation and its support networks "must undergo a revolutionary metamorphosis in order to adapt and implement change" as a result of radical innovations. Cooper (1998). The innovation could come in the shape of novel products or services, fresh processes, or fresh management approaches, Azami (2013).

2.3 Innovation and Organizational Culture

West and Farr (1990) defined innovation as the purposeful review and application of fresh ideas, processes, products, or procedures to the appropriate unit of acceptability with the aim of meaningfully advancing the individual, the group, the organisation, or wider society. Innovation, according to Hamel (1999), is a significant departure from traditional organisational structures or accepted management principles, methods, and practises that fundamentally transforms how management work is conducted. According to Christenson, invention is a condition of being that might range from having unpleasant or disturbing surroundings to having some nice ones (1997). From an OC viewpoint, Dobni (2008) continued, all of these concepts are highly contextual, and an organization's culture will affect how creative it can be. Resources, Organizational Culture (OC), and rewards are factors that affect creative behaviour in organisations, according to Woodman, Sawyer, and Griffin (1993). In a similar line, Amabile et al. (1996) found that an organization's level of creativity was influenced by how people saw their workplace. Daman Pour (1991) found that managerial receptivity to change, as well as internal and external communication, were positively connected with innovation in a study of the factors influencing organisational innovation. The company's organisational culture has a significant impact on how innovative it is, Sinkula et al. (1997). Managers require a fundamental structure in order to determine what culture should be formed to promote innovation or to determine whether a particular culture already functions as an efficient coordination tool. Organizational culture can encourage an environment that is favourable to innovation while also influencing organisational learning and abilities, according to Cameron and Quinn (2011) and Skerlavaj et al. (2013). To encourage a focus on innovation in their organisations, managers can intentionally employ organisational culture as a tool for strategic coordination, Buschgens et al. (2013). Organizational culture entirely mediates the effects of organisational innovation through organisational learning, Abdi, Senin (2014). Layers of organisational culture, including norms, artefacts, and innovative behaviours, partially mitigate the effects

of values that support innovation on measures of firm performance. Coote, Hogan (2014). Successful businesses, especially those with competent management, place a high priority on the development of tools and processes to achieve higher innovations. Unquestionably, organisational innovation is an essential part of every company's future growth and survival. With the help of innovation, institutions may better adjust to changes in the environment, the market, and customer needs. Organizational culture OC, Acar (2012), Valencia, Valle and Jiménez (2010) and management control system, on the other hand, are internal factors that will influence organisational innovation, MCS; Lopez-Valeiras, Gonzalez-Sanchez, and Gomez-Conde (2016). Also, it was found that there is a positive correlation between SMEs' digital innovation and organisational culture, according to Zhen (2021). Due to organisational resistance, organisational innovation enhances the relationship between organisational culture and effectiveness, benefiting those that promote compliance growth. Rana (2022). Since fresh ideas always inspire more ideas as part of an interaction network, organisational networks of specialists enable the establishment of entire cycles of invention. Furthermore, intrapreneurship enables people with a variety of skill sets to benefit from the synergistic impacts of related ideas.

2.4 Intrapreneurship

Intrapreneurship was defined as the employee who acts as an entrepreneur in a large and big organisation, Pinchot (1985), the risk and enterprise in an established and running organisation, Luchsinger ve Bagby(1987), the person who accepts responsibility for an innovation while working under the control of a company (Carrier, 1994), the creation of innovative new businesses both inside and outside the company, Johnson (2001), and the entrepreneurship in an established and running organisation, Anton (2003). Kenney and Mujtaba (2007). Intrapreneurship, also known as corporate entrepreneurship, is a process by which an existing organisation examines new establishment's opportunities that are fundamentally different from the current organisation, Aspelund et al. (2017), Piening and Salge (2015). The new venture frequently makes use of the operations, possessions, skills, and other resources of the former company. Using employee ingenuity to start new businesses or initiatives is known as "intrapreneurship" in corporations. There is only a slight difference between intrapreneurship and corporate entrepreneurship, claim Antoncic and Hisrich (2003). While intrapreneurship relates to the individual level and is about bottom-up, proactive work-related initiatives of individual employees, corporate entrepreneurship refers to a top-down process, i.e. a management strategy to foster workforce initiatives and efforts to innovate and develop new businesses, Piening and Salge (2015). Employees are encouraged by intrapreneurship to come up with innovative firm ideas without necessarily seeking formal management approval Azami (2013). Employees with an entrepreneurial spirit are strongly driven to take the initiative to look for new

business opportunities, Bhardwarj and Sushil Momaya (2007), Urbano and Turro (2013). However, among the intrapreneurial or corporate entrepreneurship opportunities that employees can take advantage of are: developing new business concepts that will give the company a sustainable competitive advantage; effectively utilising employees' special competencies or capabilities in generating new insight; encouraging employees' commitment and involvement in taking on new initiatives; and, among others, granting employees the freedom to work independently, Halim et al. (2017), Kacperczyk (2012), Simon and Barr (2015). Intrapreneurs in organisations have the capacity to create, recognise, and seize novel opportunities that will enable them to provide value to the organisation, Ma et al. (2016).

2.5 Innovation and Intrapreneurship

Encouragement of intrapreneurial behaviours and practises has assumed a fundamental position in many organisations' plans since doing so is considered as a crucial approach to create and maintain a competitive edge as well as a way to start corporate rejuvenation, Russel (1999). Intrapreneurship is crucial for the survival of firms through continual innovations that lead to, among other things, the production of new goods and services or the conquest of new markets, Marques et al (2019). Employee intrapreneurial behaviour has assumed critical relevance for the performance of creative enterprises, according to research by Neessen et al. (2019). It was shown that intrapreneurship is a potent indicator of the success of innovation, Gawke et al. (2017), Pandey et al. (2020). Cognitive style has a major impact on intrapreneurship and innovation outputs, which are mediated through intrapreneurship, Marques et al. (2022). Because both intuitive and rational cognitive styles hypothesise a positive relationship with intrapreneurship, intrapreneurship may function as a mediator in the relationship between cognitive styles dimensions and innovation outputs, Marques et al. (2022). Intrapreneurial activities can help the creation of an organisational competency for responsible innovation through the imprinting of the organisation. & Tatarinov, K. Ambos, T. C. (2022).

3. Proposed Design Framework

Goals and objectives of the organisation, nature of the business, organisational values, Bundhwar and Yaw (2001), policies and work environment, clients and external parties, employees, top management styles, Acar, A.Z., (2012), and organisational structure are all factors that can be used to study innovative culture, Dess et al. (2003). Adherent cultures may or may not impede the creation of novel goods or services, Valencia, J. C. N., Valle, R. S., & Jiménez, D. J. (2010). In the related cluster, a number of cultural traits interact to either promote or impede innovation performance, Mu tian et.al. (2018). Innovative Culture, according to Tushman and O'Reilly, is what drives uniqueness and creativity. According to

them and others, innovative culture has an impact on creativity and invention in a variety of ways, including the socialisation process and the value proposition that is communicated through politics, structures, and commonplace artefacts, practises, and activities. Hence, uniqueness and innovations have always been essential for a company's long-term existence and success, and they probably will be even more so in the future as it seeks to stay up with the rapid pace of market change, SantosVijande and Alvarez-Gonzalez (2007). Because they rely heavily on technology, vehicle companies need to be more creative and innovative than ever before if they want to succeed, grow, compete, and take the lead, Jung et al.(2003), Tierney et al.(1999). Managerial openness to change, as well as external and internal communications, were found to be positively connected with creativity in a study of the factors influencing innovative culture by Damanpour (1991). When considering the importance of IC , the managerial and human resource practises associated with a "innovation-supportive culture" become an intriguing research issue. By setting quantifiable, amiable objectives that prioritise the needs of the customer, businesses can prosper in creatively oriented business environments, such as the auto industry. Receiving feedback on their present products and services can help managers make incremental changes in addition to radical breakthroughs, according to M. S. Sharifirad and V. Ataei (2012). According to Brockman and Morgan (2003), there is a positive correlation between innovation and intrapreneurship, which includes adaptability. The intrapreneurs are aware of their own life's purpose, have long-term goals for each of their businesses, and are aware of their position inside those organisations. It also largely depends on subject experts, novel concepts, economic efficiency, technological brilliance, and IT solutions. They are able to maintain the extraordinary energy required for their intrapreneurial journey, which by definition seeks to deliver results that go above and beyond the call of duty, perhaps as a result of this, Seshadri and Arabinda (2006).

Innovation-driven Intrapreneurship Growth and Shifting Corporate Culture Aspects

The following key issues are explored in the model that was created: How does innovation culture within an organisation affect intrapreneurship in the commercial vehicle industry? What corporate efforts have inspired employees to embark on an intrapreneurial journey within the company? and how well did the organisation navigate after its intrapreneurship project. Innovative culture (IC), encourages intrapreneurship. According to Ping et al. (2010), the goal of intrapreneurship is to innovate across all domains and translate that innovation into company value. According to experts, intrapreneurship has essentially become a systematic approach that can be utilised to create detailed strategies and action plans that can aid in incorporating major staff contributions, Mohanty(2006). Any firm, regardless of size, must consciously foster an intrapreneurship culture that is ingrained in the mission, vision, and strategy of the organisation. A small business owner who wants to

make sure that the intrapreneurship culture informs every decision made within the organisation, Amaechi, E (2020). Adaptive innovative culture and psychological empowerment as a mediating impact mechanism were two ways that transformational leadership had positive and significant effects on employee intrapreneurial behaviour, Huynh (2021). Intrapreneurship satisfies demands by influencing the future course of businesses, and as a new subject, intrapreneurship is gaining importance. Intrapreneurship, according to Gaertner (2014), is the pursuit of entrepreneurial activity within a company to complement corporate strategy. On the other hand, social intrapreneurship calls for adaptability to embrace employee suggestions based on how workers may be inspired to operate entrepreneurially within an organisational framework, Gundogdu (2012).

Fig-1 Model of Innovative Culture's Impact on Intrapreneurship

4. Discussion- Nurturing business mindset

Using the literature review, it was possible to confirm that the term "intrapreneurship" designates a tactic that emphasises how to acquire a competitive edge. The essence of an intrapreneur, according to Orchard (2015), involves the capacity for innovation in addition to qualities like self-assurance, perseverance, willingness to take risks, and others. This behaviour might be influenced by an environment that encourages intrapreneurship, which is defined by the promotion of innovation, Orchard; Ribiere and Achtzehn, (2018). This environment encourages intrapreneurship and shapes the investments to be made in innovation within businesses. It's crucial to take into account leadership in this circumstance, Orchard; Ribiere and Achtzehn, (2018). Intrapreneurs, who guide the organisation by identifying threats and chances for both internal and external progress, play a significant role in this. Identifying the need for the adoption of new technologies is part of this search for organisational progress. Hence, innovation, technology, and intrapreneurship are factors

that, when combined, can give businesses greater outcomes and, as a result, a competitive edge. As was previously stated, the literature allows for these conclusions.

Major organisations in Commercial vehicles space that significantly invests in Research and Development, in order to stay ahead of curve, follows what we can call it as CCC framework- the three cornerstones of organisations's success, Customer – Company- Channel (Illustration 1)

The CCC framework ensures that industry progresses not just by meeting the expectation of current product but also helps industry co-create the product and service together with customer.

On first dimension, the framework backward integrates itself into the system to involve each employee in their respective domains and to enable them contribute in their own way to improve the efficiency of the operation. Each unit or division in organisation sets itself a QCD target where each employee besides their 'business as-usual' tasks contributes with ideas or suggest *Jugaad* methodology to improve his/her operations at work. This aspect balances the act of co-creating new product, service or value with that of higher efficiency and competitive cost. Therefore, the inward looking aspect of employee engagement in idea engagement, though not directly involved in external aspect co-creation, dovetails into larger organisational purpose at the end of value chain.

In the second dimension, the company and channel formulates a committee of Domain expert group [DEG] of customers in each application of their operations. For example, a manufacturer that produces Small commercial vehicles would create a DEGs in key applications such as Cement, Market load, Petroleum oil and Lubricants [POL] tankers, Construction. These DEGs are created in key application that control 70-80% of total Industry Volume [TIV]. This DEG is a quintessential form of creating market touch-point mechanism, from customers who are operating in aforesaid applications. These customers, by virtue of their experience of operation, knowledge of market and access to market policies are better equipped to guide and advise the manufacturer and dealer on efficient operating practise and much needed value generation in order to make their total cost of ownership viable and business profitable.

The third dimension of model is regulations and economic compulsions that propel innovation and upgradation. The legally binding International treaty at COP 28, Egypt to fight climate change that was adopted by 196 parties was a landmark agreement to limit global warming to 1.5 Deg compared to pre-industrial levels. In 2020, the countries submitted their plans for climate actions which included upgrading emission levels to highest level Euro 6 and use of alternate fuels to reduce the carbon foot print. Vehicular traffic contribute to roughly 27% of Green house gases [Environmental protection agency,

US]. Following this, each country has started taking slew of measures which includes migration to alternate fuels such as LPG, CNG, LNG, Battery and Hydrogen. On the other hand, the fuel importing nations have adopted higher emission norms. This dimension provides regulatory framework, a long term planning perspective to muster resources and most importantly a traction with channel and customer.

The last dimension and important link in this CCC framework is Channel. The channel is an important link in the entire value chain between Company and Customer interms of communication, coordination and coherence. The channel absorbs the supply chain shocks to the best extent possible through stocking of vehicles, finance tie ups, managing relationship with customers and bankers, managing the performance of vehicle by building ecosystem. The Company 'C' actively invests in the process to identify the gaps in processes, implementing corrective actions and most importantly ensuring dealers' viability. The Company and channel jointly reviews the processes by keeping the customer at the forefront. The channel and company devices fresh ideas through brainstorming to improve viability yet achieving customer satisfaction. For instance, moving the business credit from Letter of credit to Bank Guarantee is one such example to rationalise the cost building up in view of pricing pressure.

The CCC works similar to simultaneous engineering where three aspects namely product development, piloting of field trial vehicles and SAM [Serviceability, Accessibility and maintainability] happen at the same time during the design review. The advantage in the product context is all the three units are completely aware of the product they are working on and the definitive deliverables from each of them.

However, the CCC model is prelude or rather one step before the simultaneous engineering level. This can be called as an Macro-Micro perspective where at DEG level, it will be exploratory journey, where the organisation knows the framework of engagement based on access to technology and manufacturability of the concept into a real-time model. However, the Channel and company's inward process is a continuous improvisation of processes inorder to reach higher efficiency and cut costs. It is case where the latter prepares the supply chain for a larger possibility of tomorrow.

Illustration1.0 CCC Framework

Institutionalizing Innovation team in organisation

On the second dimension of company’s extraneous intervention, large organisations form a small, focused team. The intrapreneurship team is referred in our discussion is called as "Mission Summit" in the suggested concept and will report to the organization's Apex body (Illustration 2.0)

The summit team is made up of cross-functional teams from core functional groups, including, but not limited to, the groups responsible for production, project planning, product development, finance, marketing, and strategic sourcing. Although the group's members are operationally under the supervision and direction of the appropriate functional team, they administratively report to the Head of Mission summit unit. This organisation will guarantee two elements of fluid workflow. a) Through cross-functional, cooperative innovation, problems can be solved using the domain expertise from each function. b) Ensures ownership of the creative solutions from the relevant departments and that the best concepts with the best market judgement are combined for chain-wide value creation.

The cross-functional collaboration with diversity of ideas and in work flow is the main focus of the intrapreneurship framework model. This method enables each team member to stay up to date on their current problems and gaps in the customer value chain within their specific industry. The Mission Summit team will then brainstorm with suppliers and technology providers to create a business case that can be discussed with the Apex body. Based on strategic objective and alignment with the company's goal to allot budgets for prototyping, the apex body prioritises the list of projects.

The mission summit team involves each functional group in its specific domain while discretely involving technology providers without disrupting the organization's core operations. This covert engagement is crucial because the lengthy gestation period required for the adoption of a product, process, or strategy necessitates an incubation phase for testing, validating, and standardising it. The Mission Summit project follows its defined and typical development cycle, is followed by a bigger organisation, and choices are made by functional groups at every level up to the first batch of the finished product is released onto the market. The Mission Summit team works along with suppliers who are being watched over by the functional group to handle any teething and adaptation issues with the product. The project moves into the organization's main stream and the mission summit shifts to the next product once the product reaches a steady state volume.

In any event, this mission summit does not supplant the traditional product development team or the core functional team and deprive them of their knowledge assets. The mission summit team is utilised, however, when specific products or services that fall outside of the company's core competencies are justified and call for fresh abilities and perspectives. Rarely, with funding from IPOs and financial institutions, the parent organisation establishes a subsidiary to promote this "summit effort" mentality. As ideas from the Mission Summit become profitable commercializations, the subsidiary eventually transforms into a brand-neutral business to make the technology available to the rest of the market. The following are the advantages of having an internal or subsidiary intrapreneurship team. First and foremost, Apex puts its time, energy, and money into innovation in order to give customers something of value and long-term sustain the organization's growth. This action conveys a clear statement to the market and investors about the company's long-term viability. Second, the summit team kickstarts efforts to identify and nurture the company's talent; those who can effectively contribute to the company's long-term growth. Also, as part of this step, the business identifies a leadership pipeline to develop personnel for long-term innovation sustainability. Third, the function heads who own the respective input in the project, and who report to the mission summit team's apex body, firm up each recommendation before it is sent out for review. It is ensured that there is a sense of responsibility and accountability. Finally, in order to receive finance from financial institutions, high value projects with numerous external stakeholders typically form joint ventures or partnerships. A similar action shortens the amortisation period for each party and helps to de-risk each one.

Internal mission summits and subsidiary intrapreneurship vary primarily in that the former model integrates, utilises the backend operation, and distinguishes the front end of the business with cutting-edge products. With an own ecosystem and funding, the latter differentiates itself in both back end and front end operation. "Flexibility and freedom for disruptive thoughts" are demanded by the latter. Fascinatingly, in both situations, members

of the strategic management team and a portion of the core operating team are hand-selected to guarantee continuity in strategy, adherence to procedures, adherence to the company's value system, and alignment to goals. This guarantees that the parent company's fundamental innovative culture is adopted in "refresh" mode. In conclusion, while the structurally varied strategy paths chosen by each organisation, the implementation's core concern is the efficient use of human minds, which is strongly supported by a sustainable ecosystem that includes financing, technological access, labour, and other resources.

The "Mission Summit" (Umashankar U, Ajitha Savarimuthu, 2022) concept of cross-functional teamwork and skill diversification ensures that innovative culture-led intrapreneurship is successfully implemented at work. With time, the cross-functional collaborative work culture that results in self-assured handling of uncertainty and ongoing value creation throughout the chain becomes deeply ingrained in the organisation.

Illustration 2.0 Mission Summit

5. Conclusion

As the commercial vehicle industry undergoes one of the largest transformation at DNA level, its imperative that the industry should learn fast to adopt the contemporary matrix structure and also nurture business mind-set in each employee in its organisation. The above CCC is compelling framework in this context to engage at Macro-Micro level and also to balance between long term perspective at the sametime producing immediate results by improving efficiency of the system. The success of these small steps builds faith in the process for long term planning.

Going forward, the battery operated vehicle and any other alternate fuel operated vehicle, is expected to disrupt the Channel's viability because the absence of moving parts in the drive train unlike conventional diesel vehicle. This means that brick and mortar investment of channel will come under question.

Secondly, while operational costs of alternate fuels is economical but their acquisition cost is prohibitive by many-fold. Today, many of the public sector undertakings are emphasising on 'pay per mile' model where the asset is owned the company and lessee will pay per mile until the end of contract period. This is commercial disruption in the offing.

Thirdly, the industry is trying hard to cope up with the volume of scale in order to amortise the fresh investment and gain control of technology. On the other hand, the homologation authorities are working closely with technologists and manufacturer to finalise the testing, validating of technology at the same time ensuring safety of users and safe disposal of it at the end of life. The Eastern part of world is adept in Jugaad or Innovation by constraint which is deeply rooted in our culture due to access to resources in every aspect of our life. The west which failed to replicate Jugaad culture in their companies is now looking to East for all its cost effective manufacturing and ideas. Hence, its time to collectively engage each employee so that Indian subcontinent manufacturers would gain expertise in this transition. With the above challenges forthcoming in three dimensions, the CCC framework will provide a holistic approach to keep the company ahead of the curve.

References

Abdallah, A. B., Obeidat, B. Y., & Aqqad, N. O., 2014, The impact of supply chain management practices on supply chain performance in Jordan: The moderating effect of competitive intensity, *International Business Research*, 7(3),13-27.

Abdi, K., & Senin, A. A., 2014, Investigation on the impact of organizational culture on organization innovation, *Journal of Management Policies and Practices*, 2(2), 1-10.

Aksay, K., 2011. Yenilikçilik Kültürünün Örgütsel Yenilikçilik Üzerine Etkisi: Konya İlinde Faaliyet Gösteren Özel Hastanelerde Bir Uygulama, *Konya: Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü İşletme Anabilim Dalı*, 2 (2011), 39-63.

Ali Taha, V., Sirkova, M., & Ferencova, M., 2016, The impact of organizational culture on creativity and innovation, *Polish journal of management studies*, 14(1), 7-17.

Alvesson, M., & Sveningsson, S., 2015, *Changing organizational culture: Cultural change first edition*, Routledge.

Amabile, T. M., Conti, R., Coon, H., Lazenby, J., & Herron, M., 1996, Assessing the work environment for creativity, *Academy of management journal*, 39(5),1154-1184.

Amaechi, E, 2021. Understanding culture and success in global business: developing cultural and innovative intrapreneurs in small businesses, In *Culture in Global Businesses* (pp. 205-224), Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.

Amaechi, E., & Thomas, C. G, 2020, Perceived Relevance of Practical Skills in Content Development of Motor Vehicle Mechanic Works Trade in Technical Colleges in Nigeria for Global Competitiveness, *GSJ*, 8(12), 2165-2179.

Ambos, T. C., & Tatarinov, K. 2022, Building responsible innovation in international organizations through intrapreneurship, *Journal of Management Studies*, 59(1), 92-125.

Aminudin, M. A., Kamarudin, S. K., Lim, B. H., Majilan, E. H., Masdar, M. S., & Shaari, N, 2023, An overview: Current progress on hydrogen fuel cell vehicles, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 48(11), 4371-4388.

Antoncic, B., & Hisrich, R. D, 2003, Privatization, corporate entrepreneurship, and performance: Testing a normative model, *Journal of developmental entrepreneurship*, 8(3), 197.

Aspelund, A., Fjell, L., & Rødland, S. E, 2017, Doing good and doing well? *International journal of entrepreneurship and social responsibility*, 21(2), 13-32.

Azami, S. H. A. B. A. N. A, 2013, Intrapreneurship “an exigent employment”, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 2(4), 194-198.

Baker, K. A, 2002. *Organizational communication*, Retrieved June, 7, 2009.

Baruah, B., & Ward, A, 2015, Metamorphosis of intrapreneurship as an effective organizational strategy, *International entrepreneurship and management journal*, 11(4), 811-822.

Bhardwaj, B. R., Sushil, M. K., & Momaya, K, 2007, Corporate entrepreneurship: Application of moderator method, *Singapore Management Review*, 29(1), 47-58.

Bimpitsos, C., & Petridou, E, 2012, A transdisciplinary approach to training: preliminary research findings based on a case analysis, *European Journal of Training and Development*, 36(9), 911-929.

Bravo Rodríguez, Y., Duarte, R., & Sarasa, C. *Economic and Environmental Impacts of the Shifts to Electro-Mobility: Insights from a Multiregional and Multisectoral Approach*, Available at SSRN 4326107.

Budhwar, P, 2003, Culture and management in India, *Culture and management in Asia*, 66-81.

Büschgens, T., Bausch, A., & Balkin, D. B, 2013, Organizational culture and innovation: A meta-analytic review, *Journal of product innovation management*, 30(4), 763-781.

Cameron, K. S., & Quinn, R. E, 2011, *Diagnosing and changing organizational culture: Based on the competing values framework*, first edition, John Wiley & Sons.

Carrier, C, 1994, Intrapreneurship in large firms and SMEs: A comparative study, *International Small Business Journal*, 12(3), 54-61.

Chandler, G. N., Keller, C., & Lyon, D. W, 2000, Unraveling the determinants and consequences of an innovation-supportive organizational culture, *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 25(1), 59-76.

Chen, S., Hu, J., Zhao, L., Zhao, R., Fang, J., Shi, Y., & Xu, H, 2023, Overview. In: *Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X). Wireless Networks*. Springer, Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5130-5>

Claver, E., Llopis, J., Garcia, D., & Molina, H, 1998, Organizational culture for innovation and new technological behavior, *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 9(1), 55-68.

Cooper, J. R, 1998, A multidimensional approach to the adoption of innovation. *Management Decision*, 36, 493-502. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00251749810232565>

Daher, N, 2016, The relationships between organizational culture and organizational innovation, *International Journal of Business & Public Administration*, 13(2).53-64.

Damanpour, F, 1991, Organizational innovation: A meta-analysis of effects of determinants and moderators, *Academy of Management Journal*, 34(3), 555-590

Demirel, E. T., & Tikici, M, 2004, Kültürün girişimciliğe etkileri, *Fırat Üniversitesi Doğu Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 2(3), 49-58.

Denison, D. R., & Mishra, A. K, 1995, Toward a theory of organizational culture and effectiveness, *Organization science*, 6(2), 204-223.

Desreveaux, A., Bouscayrol, A., Trigui, R., Hittinger, E., Castex, E., & Sirbu, G. M. 2023, Accurate energy consumption for comparison of climate change impact of thermal and electric vehicles, *Energy*, Elsevier, vol. 268(C).

Dess, G. G., Ireland, R. D., Zahra, S. A., Floyd, S. W., Janney, J. J., & Lane, P. J, 2003, Emerging issues in corporate entrepreneurship, *Journal of management*, 29(3), 351-378.

Dobni, C. B, 2008, Measuring innovation culture in organizations: The development of a generalized innovation culture construct using exploratory factor analysis, *European journal of innovation management*,11(4), 539-559.

Dundar, H., Millot, B., Savchenko, Y., Aturupane, H., & Piyasiri, T. A, 2014, Building the skills for economic growth and competitiveness in Sri Lanka, World Bank Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-1-4648-0158-7>

Edmondson, A. C., & Mogelof, J. P, 2006, Explaining psychological safety in innovation teams: organizational culture, team dynamics, or personality?, In *Creativity and innovation in organizational teams*, Psychology Press, 129-156,

EY-Japan, 2013, The EY G20 Entrepreneurship Barometer 2013 - Country Report: Japan, Ernst & Young Global Limited, EYG no. CY0569. ED 0715

Farr, J. L., & Ford, C. M, 1990, Individual innovation, In: West, M.A. and Farr, J.L., Eds., *Innovation and Creativity at Work: Psychological and Organisational Strategies*, Wiley, Chichester, 63-80.

Fey, C. F., & Denison, D. R, 2003, Organizational culture and effectiveness: Can American theory be applied in Russia?, *Organization science*, 14(6), 686-706.

French, W. L., Kast, F. E., & Rosenzweig, J. E. 1985, *Understanding human behavior in organizations*, / Wendell L. French, Fremont E. Kast, James E. Rosenzweig, book published by Harper & Row.

Gaertner, M. A, 2014, *Applying intrapreneurship to sustain corporate growth: A business practitioner's model* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Maryland University College).

Gawke, J. C., Gorgievski, M. J., & Bakker, A. B ,2017, Employee intrapreneurship and work engagement: A latent change score approach, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 100, 88–100.

Giang, H. T. T., & Dung, L. T, 2021, Transformational leadership and non-family employee intrapreneurial behaviour in family-owned firms: the mediating role of adaptive culture and psychological empowerment, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 42 No. 8, pp. 1185-1205. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-03-2021-0116>

Gündoğdu, M. Ç, 2012, Re-thinking entrepreneurship, intrapreneurship, and innovation: A multi-concept perspective, *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 41, 296-303.

Hamel, G, 1996, Strategy as revolution (pp. 69-82), Nova York: Harvard Business Review.

Hamel, G,1999, Bringing silicon valley inside, *Harvard business review*, 77(5), 71-71.

Hogan, S. J., & Coote, L. V, 2014, Organizational culture, innovation, and performance: A test of Schein's model, *Journal of business research*, 67(8), 1609-1621.

Huynh, Q, 2021, The effect of organizational culture on quality of accounting information: Mediating the role of accounting information system, *Accounting*, 7(7), 1689-1694.

Imber, A, 2013, Breakthrough innovation vs. disruptive innovation, Retrieved December, 12, 2017.

Ireland, R. D., Hitt, M. A., & Sirmon, D. G, 2003, A model of strategic entrepreneurship: The construct and its dimensions, *Journal of management*, 29(6), 963-989.

Johnson, D. 2001, What is innovation and entrepreneurship? Lessons for larger organisations, *Industrial and Commercial Training*, Vol. 33 No. 4, pp. 135-140. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00197850110395245>.

Jung, D. I., Chow, C., & Wu, A, 2003, The role of transformational leadership in enhancing organizational innovation: Hypotheses and some preliminary findings, *The leadership quarterly*, 14(4-5), 525-544.

Kacperczyk, A. J, 2012, Opportunity structures in established firms: Entrepreneurship versus intrapreneurship in mutual funds, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 57(3), 484-521.

Kang, H. J., Gatling, A., & Kim, J, 2015, The impact of supervisory support on organizational commitment, career satisfaction, and turnover intention for hospitality frontline employees, *Journal of Human Resources in Hospitality & Tourism*, 14(1), 68-89.

Kenney, M., & Mujtaba, B. G, 2007, Understanding corporate entrepreneurship and development: A practitioner view of organizational intrapreneurship, *Journal of Applied Management and Entrepreneurship*, 12(3), 73-88.

Klein, A., & Krcmar, H, 2006, DCXNET: e-transformation at DaimlerChrysler, *Journal of information technology*, 21(1), 52-65.

Laužikas, M., Miliūtė, A., Baltaduonis, T., & Mačiulskis, Ž, 2022, Impacts of modern technologies while identifying and unleashing intrapreneurs' potential, *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 10(2), 217-238.

Li-Hsing, H., Ya-Ping, W., Hung-Chen, H., & Hsueh-Chih, C, 2011, Influence of humorous leadership at workplace on the innovative behavior of leaders and their leadership effectiveness, *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(16), 6673-6683.

Llopis-Albert, C., Rubio, F., & Valero, F, 2021, Impact of digital transformation on the automotive industry, *Technological forecasting and social change*, 162, 120343. DOI:[10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120343](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120343).

Lopez-Valeiras, E., Gonzalez-Sanchez, M. B., & Gomez-Conde, J., 2016, The effects of the interactive use of management control systems on process and organizational innovation, *Review of Managerial Science*, 10(3), 487-510.

Luchsinger, V., & Bagby, D. R., 1987, Entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship: Behaviors, comparisons, and contrasts, *SAM Advanced Management Journal*, 52(3), 10.

Malik, R. K., & Sinha, G. K., 2020, Sustainable Logistics in Automobile Passenger Vehicle Manufacturing Organizations, *International Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences*, 6(2), 1-9.

Manley, S. C., Hair, J. F., Williams, R. I., & McDowell, W. C., 2021, Essential new PLS-SEM analysis methods for your entrepreneurship analytical toolbox, *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 17(4), 1805-1825.

Marques, C. S., Lopes, C., Braga, V., Ratten, V., & Santos, G., 2022, Intuition and rationality in intrapreneurship and innovation outputs: The case of health professionals in primary health care, *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 18(2), 579-602.

Memili, E., Lumpkin, G. T., & Dess, G. G., 2010, Entrepreneurial orientation: the driving force for corporate entrepreneurship, In *Handbook of research on strategy process*, Edward Elgar Publishing.

Mohanty, R. P., 2006, Intrapreneurial levers in cultivating value-innovative mental space in Indian corporations, *Vikalpa*, 31(1), 99-106.

Mohsin, A. M. B. A., Halim, H. A., & Farhana, N., 2017, Assessing the role of entrepreneurial competencies on innovation performance: A partial least squares (PLS) approach, *The Journal of Business Inquiry*, 16(1 Spec), 88-101.

Naveed, R. T., Alhaidan, H., Al Halbusi, H., & Al-Swidi, A. K., 2022, Do organizations really evolve? The critical link between organizational culture and organizational innovation toward organizational effectiveness: Pivotal role of organizational resistance, *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 7(2), 100178.

Neessen, P., Caniëls, M. C., Vos, B., & De Jong, J. P., 2019, The intrapreneurial employee: toward an integrated model of intrapreneurship and research agenda, *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 15(2), 545-571.

Odor, H. O. (2018), Organisational culture and dynamics, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 18(A1), 23–29. Retrieved from <https://journalofbusiness.org/index.php/GJMBR/article/view/2406>

Oladinrin, O. T., Arif, M., Rana, M. Q., & Gyoh, L, 2022, Interrelations between construction ethics and innovation: a bibliometric analysis using VOSviewer, *Construction Innovation*, Vol. 23 No. 3, pp. 505-523.

Orchard, S, 2015, Entrepreneurship and the human capital of organizational innovation: The intrapreneur, In *The entrepreneurial rise in Southeast Asia* Palgrave Macmillan, New York, (pp. 111-138).

Orchard, S., Ribiere, V., & Achtzehn, D, 2018, The influence of the leader and led relationship on the intrapreneurship environment in UK SMEs, *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 24(3), 1-19.

Panda, S., Srivastava, S., & Pandey, S. C, 2020, Nature and evolution of trust in business-to-business settings: Insights from VC-entrepreneur relationships, *Industrial Marketing Management*, 91, 246-256.

Parboteeah, K. P, 2000, Choice of type of corporate entrepreneurship: a process model, *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 6(1), 28-47.

Paunovic, S., & Dima, I. C, 2014, Organizational culture and corporate entrepreneurship, *Annals of the University of Petroşani, Economics*, 14, 269-276.

Piening, E. P., & Salge, T. O, 2015, Understanding the antecedents, contingencies, and performance implications of process innovation: A dynamic capabilities perspective, *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 32(1), 80-97.

Pinchot III, G, 1985, Intrapreneuring: Why you don't have to leave the corporation to become an entrepreneur, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign's Academy for Entrepreneurial Leadership Historical Research Reference in Entrepreneurship, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1496196>

Poole Jr, R. W, 2023, Tolling Value Proposition for Trucking and State Departments of Transportation, *Transportation Research*, 2677(2), 328- 344.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/03611981221147048>

Rodriguez-Pomeda, J., Navarrete, F. C. F. D., Morcillo-Ortega, P., & Rodriguez-Anton, J. M, 2003, The figure of the intrapreneur in driving innovation and initiative for the firm's transformation, *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management*, 3(4), 349-357.

Rothberg, R. R, 1981, *Product innovation in perspective*, Corporate Strategy and Product Innovation, University of Michigan, first edition, 1-13.

Russel, R. D, 1999, Developing a process model of intrapreneurial systems: A cognitive mapping approach, *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 23(3), 65-84.

Sanz-Valle, R., Naranjo-Valencia, J. C., Jiménez-Jiménez, D., & Perez-Caballero, L, 2011, Linking organizational learning with technical innovation and organizational culture, *Journal of knowledge management*, 15(6), 997-1015.

Schilling, M. A, 2005, *Strategic management of technological innovation (Vol. 3)*, New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.

Seshadri, D.V.R., & Arabinda Tripathy, 2006, Innovation through Intrapreneurship: The Road Less Travelled, *Vikalpa*, 31, 17-29.

Sharifirad, M. S., & Ataei, V, 2012, Organizational culture and innovation culture: exploring the relationships between constructs, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 33(5), pp. 494-517.

Simon, R., & Barr, C, 2015, Endangered species: Young US entrepreneurs, *Wall Street Journal*.

Singh, C. D, 2015, Role of Manufacturing Competency in Strategic Success of A Commercial Vehicle Manufacturing Unit: A Case Study, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(10), 24-41.

Sinkula, J. M., Baker, W. E., & Noordewier, T, 1997, A framework for market-based organizational learning: Linking values, knowledge, and behavior, *Journal of the academy of Marketing Science*, 25(4), 305-318.

Škerlavaj, M., Su, C., & Huang, M, 2013, The moderating effects of national culture on the development of organisational learning culture: A multilevel study across seven countries, *Journal for East European Management Studies*, 97-134.

Socolich, S. A., Blanco, M., Hanowski, R. J., Olson, R. L., Morgan, J. F., Guo, F., & Wu, S. C, 2013, An analysis of driving and working hour on commercial motor vehicle driver safety using naturalistic data collection, *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 58, 249-258.

Siyu Teng, Xuemin Hu, Peng Deng, Bai Li, Yuchen Li, Dongsheng Yang, Yunfeng Ai, Lingxi Li, Zhe Xuanyuan, Fenghua Zhu, Long Chen, 2023, Motion planning for autonomous driving: The state of the art and future perspectives, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.09824>.

Thompson, A. A., & Strickland III, A. J, 1987, *Strategic Management: Concept and Cases*, 1987, Business Publication, Texas, USA.

Tian, M., Deng, P., Zhang, Y., & Salmador, M. P, 2018, How does culture influence innovation? A systematic literature review, *Management Decision*, ol. 56 No. 5, pp. 1088-1107.

Tierney, P., Farmer, S. M., & Graen, G. B, 1999, An examination of leadership and employee creativity: The relevance of traits and relationships, *Personnel psychology*, 52(3), 591-620.

Turró, A., Urbano, D., & Peris-Ortiz, M, 2014, Culture and innovation: The moderating effect of cultural values on corporate entrepreneurship, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 88, 360-369.

Umashankar U,Ajitha Savarimuthu, 2022, Development of intrapreneurship through organizational culture- A Design Framework, *Manager -The British Journal of Administrative Management*,Vol:58; Issue 155, 138-154

Valencia, J C. N., Valle, R. S., & Jiménez, D. J, 2010, Organizational culture as determinant of product innovation, *European journal of innovation management*, Vol. 13 No. 4, pp. 466-480.

Vikas, A. V., & Guptha, N. S,2018, Secure of Data on stored Cloud from Decentralized Access Control with Anonymous Authentication, *Asian Journal of Engineering and Technology Innovation (AJETI)*, 200-204.

Wappelhorst, S., Morrison, K., & Wilkens, M,2023, An Equitable Transition From Combustion Engines To Battery Electric Vehicles.

Winkelhake, U., Winkelhake, & Schilgerius, 2018, *Digital transformation of the automotive industry*, New York, NY: Springer International Publishing AG.

Woodman, R. W., Sawyer, J. E., & Griffin, R. W, 1993, Toward a theory of organizational creativity, *Academy of management review*, 18(2), 293-321.

Yıldız, S., Baştürk, F., & Boz, İ. T, 2014, The effect of leadership and innovativeness on business performance, *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150, 785-793.

Zhang, X., Ma, X., Wang, Y., Li, X., & Huo, D, 2016, What drives the internationalization of Chinese SMEs? The joint effects of international entrepreneurship characteristics, network ties, and firm ownership, *International Business Review*, 25(2), 522-534.

Zhen, Z., Yousaf, Z., Radulescu, M., & Yasir, M, 2021. Nexus of digital organizational culture, capabilities, organizational readiness, and innovation: Investigation of SMEs operating in the digital economy, *Sustainability*, 13(2), 720.